

Time Series forecasting of daily ICU admissions. SARIMA model development and validation.

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Abstract

Background Accurate forecasting of intensive care unit (ICU) admissions is critical to optimize resource allocation, improve patients' outcomes, and maintain hospital readiness. Time series models, particularly Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA), are increasingly used in healthcare settings for short-term demand forecasting but remain underutilized for ICU admissions. **Objectives** The primary objective was to identify the most suitable ARIMA or SARIMA model for forecasting daily ICU admissions. Secondary objectives included generating forecasts for a one-month period and comparing the predicted values to actual ICU admission counts to evaluate model performance. **Methods** This was a retrospective observational time series analysis of ICU admissions. The study used 28 months (January 2023–April 2025) of retrospective daily ICU admission data to fit the model, and admissions from May 2025 for validation. Model selection was performed using the `auto.arima` function in R, optimizing for the lowest Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), with several model diagnostics. Actual admissions were inspected within the 80% and 95% prediction intervals. **Results** The best-fitting model was ARIMA (0, 1, 1) (2, 0, 1)[7], indicating weekly seasonality, with AIC (3340.4) and showed significant improvement in predictive accuracy over the naïve model, with RMSE and MAE ratios of 0.8 and Diebold-Mariano test p value < 0.0001. The empirical 95% and 80% prediction interval coverage was 1 and 0.77 respectively. **Conclusion** ARIMA models, particularly those accounting for seasonal patterns, can reliably forecast daily ICU admissions with good short-term accuracy. Integrating such models into hospital operations may improve readiness, reduce overcrowding, and support proactive critical care planning. Slight overestimation observed in predictions may be preferable to underestimation, which carries greater clinical risk.

Keywords: ICU, Admission, ARIMA, SARIMA, Prediction.

Introduction

Accurately forecasting intensive care unit (ICU) admissions is vital for effective hospital planning, resource allocation, and patient safety (1). The demand for ICU services is inherently variable, influenced by seasonal patterns, disease outbreaks, demographic factors, and emergency events (2). When ICU capacity is exceeded, hospitals may face delays in admitting critically ill patients (3), which is associated with adverse outcomes such as prolonged mechanical ventilation, increased length of hospital stay, and higher mortality rates (4-6). Ensuring the timely availability of ICU beds is therefore not only a logistical priority but also a clinical necessity (7, 8).

Forecasting tools can help anticipate daily ICU admission volumes, allowing healthcare administrators to plan staffing levels, manage bed occupancy, and mobilize resources in advance (9). Among the various approaches to time series forecasting, the Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model has gained recognition for its versatility and predictive accuracy. ARIMA models are particularly well-suited to modeling data with trends and autocorrelation, which are common in healthcare time series (10-13).

ARIMA is a class of statistical models that explains a time series based on its own past values (autoregressive component), the difference between values to achieve stationarity (integrated component), and past forecast errors (moving average component) (14). The model is typically denoted as ARIMA(p , d , q), where p represents the number of autoregressive terms, d the degree of differencing needed to make the series stationary, and q the number of lagged forecast errors in the prediction equation. Additionally, ARIMA can be extended to handle seasonal patterns through seasonal terms, yielding models such as SARIMA (Seasonal ARIMA) (14, 15).

Despite its proven effectiveness in fields such as economics, meteorology, and industrial forecasting, the application of ARIMA models in healthcare—especially for ICU demand forecasting—remains underexplored. This study aims to fill that gap by developing an ARIMA-based model to forecast daily ICU admissions using retrospective data from ICU, and validating the model using prospective data. By identifying temporal trends and seasonal fluctuations in ICU admissions, the study seeks to enhance hospital readiness and reduce the risks associated with delayed access to intensive care.

Method

Study objectives

The primary objective was to identify the most suitable ARIMA or SARIMA model that fits our data. Secondary objectives were predicting the number of daily ICU admissions for a month, and comparing the predicted numbers to the actual admission numbers.

Study design, timeframe, and setting

This was an observational retrospective time series analysis. To build our model, we used the number of daily ICU admissions of over two years (January 2023 to April 2025) in the form of a time series, while the daily admissions during May 2025 were used for validation of the forecast model.

The study was conducted in the ICU of the largest government hospital in the central region in Saudi Arabia. The hospital has a power of 1200 inpatient beds, while the ICU harbors 110 beds divided into several units. Namely, medical, surgical, respiratory, trauma, neuro-critical, obstetrics and gynecology, and burn units. All ICU beds are fully equipped with invasive and non-invasive monitoring and

ventilation capabilities. The ICU is run round the clock by intensivists, with a nurse to patient ratio of one to one.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The time series of daily ICU admissions included all admissions to the ICU regardless of their source, duration of ICU stay, or ICU outcome. This included admissions from the emergency department, the operative room, general wards, or admission by fax from other hospitals. Any admission was counted regardless whether they were newly admitted or re-admitted to the ICU. We included admissions to any unit of the ICU without exception.

Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the local IRB of our hospital (H1QI-14-Aug25-01), with waiver of consent, in view of its observational nature. However, the study observes research subjects' rights as outlined by the declaration of Helsinki. Anonymized data with no personal identifiers were made publicly available, and can be downloaded from: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/waleedaletreby/arima-prediction-of-icu-daily-admission>

Statistical Analysis

The time series analysis of daily ICU admissions was performed using the Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA) modeling framework. ARIMA models are widely used for analyzing and forecasting univariate time series data. The general ARIMA model is denoted as ARIMA (p, d, q), where: p is the number of autoregressive (AR) terms, d is the degree of differencing needed to make the series stationary, and q is the number of lagged forecast errors in the prediction equation (moving average terms). This model captures different aspects of temporal dependence in the data. The autoregressive component models the relationship between an observation and its previous values, while the moving average component models the relationship between an observation and a residual error from a moving average model applied to lagged observations. The differencing parameter addresses non-stationarity by transforming the series into a stationary one (16, 17).

To account for potential seasonal patterns in ICU admissions (e.g., weekly or monthly cycles), we considered Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) models, denoted as ARIMA (p, d, q) (P, D, Q) [s], where the uppercase letters represent the seasonal autoregressive (P), seasonal differencing (D), and seasonal moving average (Q) terms, and [s] indicates the seasonal period (e.g., s = 7 for weekly seasonality in daily data). Stationarity of the time series is a prerequisite for fitting ARIMA models. To assess whether the original or differenced series is stationary, we applied the Kwiatkowski–Phillips–Schmidt–Shin (KPSS) test, for which the null hypothesis is that data is stationary. Accordingly, a p value of < 0.05 for KPSS test indicates that the data is non-stationary (17, 18).

Model selection was performed using the (*auto.arima*) function, which automatically identifies the optimal (p, d, q) with or without (P, D, Q) parameters based on the lowest Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Further refining of the model was implemented with possible manual addition of (p, d, q) or (P, D, Q) terms according to evaluation of the model's residuals. The selected model was then used to generate out-of-sample forecasts for daily ICU admissions over the upcoming month (18).

Model adequacy was assessed by inspecting residual plots, conducting the “Ljung-Box” test for autocorrelation in the residuals, and examining forecast accuracy using standard metrics such as Mean

Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), compared to a naïve model. We used the final model to predict admissions for May 2025, and plotted the 95% and the 80% prediction intervals (PI) of the predictions against the actual number of admissions, and the accuracy of predictions were compared to those of the naïve model using “Diebold-Mariano”.

All analyses were conducted using R software (19), and a significance level of 0.05 was used for all hypothesis testing.

Sample Size Justification

Formal sample size calculations are not typically applicable to time series modeling approaches such as ARIMA, as these models do not rely on hypothesis testing in the conventional sense. Instead, forecasting performance depends on the amount and quality of temporal data available, including the length of the observation period, frequency of data points, and underlying data characteristics such as trend, seasonality, and noise. Nevertheless, several guidelines recommend a minimum of 50–100 observations for simple ARIMA models, and more than 200–300 observations for models with seasonal or complex structures. Some sources suggest that >500 time points are ideal for capturing reliable temporal dependencies and achieving robust forecasting performance, especially in healthcare settings where daily data can be highly variable (20). In this study, we used 28 months of daily ICU admissions data (851 daily data points), which exceeds commonly accepted thresholds for time series modeling. This duration provides sufficient data to detect trends, seasonality, and autocorrelation, and to fit and validate a well-performing ARIMA or SARIMA model.

Results

During the period between January 2023 and April 2025 there were 8750 admissions to the ICU, with a median daily admission of ten patients, inter-quartile range (IQR) four, with a maximum admissions in one day of twenty-two patients, and a minimum of two patients.

When the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the time series was examined, it showed that many autocorrelation bars lied outside the red 95% confidence bounds, indicating that significant autocorrelation exists. It also showed that many ACF values persist at different lags (not dying off quickly), likely indicating non-stationary or seasonal behavior (figure 1).

Whereas, the partial autocorrelation function (PACF) showed significant spikes at early lags (1–5) suggesting short-term autoregressive relationships. After that, the PACF mostly stays within bounds, indicating higher-order lags may not add predictive value. This pattern might suggest that the time series has direct dependence on the past 2–3 values (figure 2). Non-stationarity of the time series was confirmed by a statistically significant p value of KPSS test of < 0.01.

The function *auto.arima* was used along with multiple fine tuning modifications based on visual evaluation of model’s residuals, and p values of “Ljung-Box” test. The best model to fit our data was found to have no autoregressive (AR) terms ($p = 0$), one non-seasonal difference ($d = 1$) to achieve stationarity, one non-seasonal moving average (MA) term ($q = 1$), and a seasonal component consisting of two seasonal auto-regressive (SAR) terms ($P = 2$), and one seasonal moving average (SMA) term, (with a periodicity of [7], suggesting weekly seasonality {SARIMA (0, 1, 1) (2, 0, 1) [7]}), figure 3 shows the model residuals. This model had the lowest AIC of 3340.4 among all evaluated models. Stationarity of the model was confirmed by KPSS test, which yielded a p value = 0.1. Similarly, the model errors were improved compared to the naïve model (Table 1), representing an approximate 33% improvement in forecast accuracy, indicating that the ARIMA model provides a substantially better fit to the data (21).

Additionally, adequacy of the model was confirmed by a statistically non-significant p values of “Ljung-Box” test on model residuals ($p = 0.2$ at 24 lags), indicating stationary residuals. Figure 4 shows the inverse roots of the AR and MA parts of the fitted model. The points are plotted on the complex plane with a unit circle for reference. All points fall inside the unit circle, which means the model is both stable (stationary) and invertible. This suggests that the model is appropriate and reliable for forecasting.

When the model’s accuracy was ascertained, it was used to predict the number of daily ICU admissions in May 2025. The actual numbers of daily ICU admissions were all within the 95% and mostly within the 80% PI. “Diebold-Mariano” test comparing accuracy of prediction to naïve model yielded p value < 0.0001 , the empirical 80% prediction interval coverage was 77%, whereas that of 95% prediction interval was 100% (figure 5).

Discussion

In this study, we developed and validated a Seasonal ARIMA model to forecast daily ICU admissions using over two years of retrospective data and evaluated its performance over a one-month period. The selected model, SARIMA (0,1,1)(2,0,1)[7], incorporated weekly seasonality and achieved good predictive accuracy, with 100% and 77% empirical coverage of the 95% and 80% PIs, respectively.

Our findings demonstrate that time series models can be effectively applied to forecast ICU admissions in a high-volume tertiary care setting. The forecasted values were fairly accurate, and the model significantly outperformed the naïve forecast in terms of both MAE and RMSE. This supports the utility of ARIMA modeling for short-term hospital resource planning, particularly in settings with predictable admission patterns and sufficient historical data.

These results are consistent with previous studies that reported successful use of ARIMA models in healthcare demand forecasting. For example, Dalili et al. (10) applied ARIMA modeling to neonatal ICU admissions and mortality, achieving satisfactory forecast accuracy. Similarly, Murray et al. (11) combined time series and survival models to forecast ICU census, indicating that ARIMA-based methods are competitive and feasible in clinical applications. However, our study contributes further by integrating model validation through unseen data.

The detected weekly seasonality in our data (captured through seasonal moving average terms with a period of 7) may reflect cyclic patterns, probably as a result of varying census and occupancy in the ICU. Recognizing and modeling these regularities is crucial for reliable forecasting. Moreover, the use of diagnostic tools such as the ACF, PACF, and KPSS test prior to model fitting ensured that the assumptions of the ARIMA framework were appropriately addressed.

Although results of this study indicate that ARIMA forecasting could be reliably implemented by hospitals and ICUs to predict daily demand, which aids in pro-active allocation of resources. However, our model seemed to over-estimate the number of ICU admissions in most of the predicted days. Indeed, it is a characteristic of ARIMA models to slightly overestimate forecasts (22), and this over-estimation was observed in a similar study forecasting ICU census using a similar model (23). Over-forecasting admissions may be viewed as wasted resources that might have been more efficiently utilized if deployed elsewhere within the hospital (24). However, we must not overlook the potential harms associated with under-estimation, such as delayed ICU

admission, along with over-crowding of emergency departments, both of which carry well documented harms and risks (5, 25).

Despite the strengths of our study, several limitations should be noted. First, the model is univariate and does not account for external predictors such as outbreaks, policy changes, or staffing levels that may affect ICU admissions. Including exogenous variables in future work using ARIMAX or machine learning models could enhance predictive performance. Second, although the model performed well in the short term, forecasting accuracy may degrade over longer horizons or during unexpected surges in demand, such as pandemics or disasters. Third, this study was conducted in a single center with a large ICU; generalizability to smaller or more variable institutions may be limited. Finally, we included readmitted patients, which may influence independency of data, however, we wanted to capture all admissions, as they all occupy beds in ICU, and utilize resources, regardless of whether they were readmissions or not.

Future research should explore ensemble approaches that combine ARIMA with machine learning or epidemiological models to enhance robustness, especially in volatile healthcare environments. Additionally, integration of such forecasting models into hospital information systems may enable real-time, data-driven decisions about staffing, elective scheduling, and surge capacity planning.

Conclusion

Our findings support the feasibility and utility of using ARIMA models to forecast ICU admissions with reasonable accuracy. Incorporating such tools into hospital planning processes could improve readiness and patient flow, ultimately enhancing critical care delivery.

Authors' contribution

AM (Supervision, Conceptualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing).

RA (Conceptualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

HH (Methodology, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

AA (Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing).

BA (Data curation, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

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AA (Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

WA (Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Project administration, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

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Conflict of interest

None declared

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Figure 1 Autocorrelation function

Many autocorrelation bars outside the red 95% confidence bounds, indicating significant autocorrelation

Figure 2 Partial Autocorrelation function

Significant spikes at early lags (1–5) suggesting short-term autoregressive relationships.

Figure 3: Final SARIMA model residuals:

Residual diagnostics of the final model demonstrate approximate normality, absence of significant autocorrelation, and homoscedastic variance, suggesting that the underlying model assumptions are adequately satisfied.

Figure 4: Inverse Roots of SARIMA Model Polynomials

Inverse roots of the characteristic polynomials of the fitted ARIMA model. The left panel displays the inverse autoregressive (AR) roots, and the right panel shows the inverse moving average (MA) roots. Each point corresponds to a root, plotted on the complex plane with the unit circle drawn as reference.

Figure 5: Actual daily ICU admissions, with 80% and 95% PI.

Lo80 = lower bound 80% prediction interval, Hi80 = upper bound 80% prediction interval, Lo95 = lower bound 95% prediction interval, Hi95 = upper bound 95% prediction interval

Table 1: Final model comparison to naïve prediction:

<i>Model</i>	<i>AIC</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>MPE</i>	<i>MAPE</i>	<i>MASE</i>	<i>ACF1</i>
<i>Naive</i>	<i>3390</i>	<i>-0.004</i>	<i>4.03</i>	<i>3.2</i>	<i>-9.04</i>	<i>34.3</i>	<i>1.1</i>	<i>-0.5</i>
<i>SARIMA</i>	<i>3340.4</i>	<i>0.003</i>	<i>2.71</i>	<i>2.1</i>	<i>-7.89</i>	<i>23.5</i>	<i>0.7</i>	<i>-0.09</i>

AIC = Akaike Information Criterion, ME = Mean Error, RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error, MAE = Mean Absolute Error, MPE = Mean Percentage Error, MAPE = Mean Absolute Percentage Error, MASE = Mean Absolute Scaled Error, ACF1 = Autocorrelation of errors at lag 1